

Björn Kurtén

Centenary Symposium

Poster abstract booklet

Table of Contents

PREFACE	2
KURTÉN, B.: Great White Chark seen as prototype for Imperial Ichthyosaur	3
BAKHIA, A.: Environmental volatility and its impact on faunal communities: Insights from Kvabebi (Republic of Georgia)	5
DOUGLAS, R.: Determining dietary variation and its palaeoecological implications of <i>Mammuthus primigenius</i> using mesowear angle analysis	7
FOISTER, T.I.F & WILSON, O.E.: Anthropocentrism as a source of sampling bias in the fossil record	8
GEORGE VARGHESE, M., STENBERG, O., SOVA, S. & JERNVALL, J.: Unraveling the complexity of cave bear molars: the influence of enamel distribution and enamel dentine junction shape	9
GLÖGGLER, J., MURIUKI, R.M., PARKER, A.K., RIERA, D.B., SAARINEN, J., CABEZA JAIMEJUAN, M., KINYANJUI, R.N. & ŽLIOBAITĚ, I.: Macroevolution of functional traits in mammal communities in the Pliocene to modern Omo-Turkana Basin	10
HIRVONEN, R.: Comparison of carpal and tarsal bone anatomy of cave bears and modern ursids	12
KAFFASH HOSHIAR, A., STENBERG, O., HALLIKAS, O. & JERNVALL, J.: Using a Single Gene to Gradually Increase Tooth Complexity	13
KOROLAINEN, R.: Fine-tuned optical character recognition for dental fossil markings	14
LOPEZALLES, S.: The shape of speed: using 3D humerus shape to track the evolution of cursoriality in fossil canids	15
MBETE MBATHA, P., SAARINEN, J. & JERNVALL, J.: Proboscidean post-cranial morphometrics and ecomorphology and their utility in reconstructing past environments	16
MURIUKI, R.M., GLÖGGLER, J., KINYANJUI, R.N. & ŽLIOBAITĚ, I.: Plant functional traits as a proxy to reconstruct climate and mammal interactions: links in modern to Miocene ecosystems in Eastern Africa	17
NUMMELA, S. & VIRANTA, S.: What did <i>Ursus spelaeus</i> hear? Auditory abilities of the cave bear	18
PARKER, A.K. LIU, L., PUSHKINA, D. & ŽLIOBAITĚ, I.: Assessment of bias in Pleistocene mammal assemblages and application of recommender systems to improve fossil community sampling	19
PÄTILÄ, I.: The ecology of extinct birds during the Late Pleistocene and its implications to the Late Quaternary extinction event	21
PUSHKINA, D.: Pleistocene paleoecology and body mass of horses in northern Eurasia	22
RAZMADZE, D., EYMANN, J. & DI-POÏ, N.: Tooth development and diversity in squamate reptiles	23
SESTRICK, K.: How do developmental constraints and functional demands affect evolution of the mammalian post-canine dentition?	24
SOVA, S., GEORGE VARGHESE, M., HÄKKINEN, T., TJÄDERHANE, L. & JERNVALL, J.: Detecting the phenotypic effect of rickets in human molars	25
SPIRIDONOV, A., DAUMANTAS, L. & ELDREDGE, N.: Bretskyan hierarchy, geobiomes and the epoch-scale Miocene contiguous USA mammalian paleobiogeography – the HespDiv approach	26
STENBERG, O., VIRANTA, S. & JERNVALL, J.: Shearing a developmental rule	27
WILSON, O.E. & SAARINEN, J.: Application of mesowear to leontiniid notoungulates: diet in <i>Taubatherium paulacoutoi</i>	28
ZUBAID, S., SAARINEN, J. & ŽLIOBAITĚ, I.: Dental ecometrics as a tracer of climatic change during Late Neogene in the Siwaliks	30

Preface

One legacy of Björn Kurtén's palaeontological career is exemplified by the diversity of work still carried out by his intellectual descendents, decades on from his passing. His own research was defined by clarity of thought, curiosity and pragmatism, but alongside his research, Kurtén is remembered fondly for the time and energy he gave to training the next generation. During the centenary celebration of his life, works and legacy, the Björn Kurtén Centenary Symposium Planning Group wanted to reflect this through a poster session, with posters primarily presented by students and postdocs, as well as any other eager participants. In addition, we felt that the centenary celebration was the perfect place to include a long-unpublished manuscript of Kurtén's, found and kindly scanned by Mikael Fortelius. We have included this manuscript unedited in this abstract booklet.

You will notice that the topics covered here include (but are not limited to) some of Kurtén's personal favourites: teeth (their development and their functional relationship to the environment), carnivores, Pleistocene Eurasia. The abstracts also highlight how international the palaeontological community in Finland has become since the days of Kurtén, both in terms of fields of study and country of origin of the researchers moving here. The future of the palaeontological culture in Finland has never felt so bright, and we are certain that Kurtén would have been delighted by this.

We are deeply grateful to the Societas Scientiarum Fennica, Nordenskiöld Samfundet and Suomen Paleontologinen Seura for their support throughout the planning of the poster session and the rest of the symposium, and to the team at Annales Zoologici Fennici (particularly Krzysztof Raciborski) for their dedicated work producing the special volume accompanying the celebration (in which fuller accounts of some of the abstracts here are given). We also thank the authors of all abstracts included here for their participation and the high quality of all work included.

Björn Kurtén Centenary Symposium Planning Group

Oscar Wilson, Susanna Sova, Henry Pihlström, Juha Saarinen, Indrė Žliobaitė, Suvi Viranta, Ian Corfe,
Janina Rannikko

Cover image: Homotherium, originally produced by Hubert Pepper, used with permission of Suomen Paleontologinen Seura

Great White Chark seen as prototype for Imperial Ichthyosaur

Björn Kurtén^{1*}

1. Department of Geology, University of Helsinki, Snellmaninkatu SF-00170 Helsinki, Finland

“I think how it to do I know” G. von Schimpfen-Witzen, Deathless Metaphors

A convincing theory of chark origins must clarify their relationships with living fish and with the ancestors of fish known, if doubtfully, from fossils. In this paper, we show that Chark history conforms with the clockwise type of evolution from which we have demonstrated in several papers in PASTURE and elsewhere, and which has recently been challenged by the anticlockwise theory of Bungler et al. (*alias* Latimer et al. 1981).

Elsewhere (Banture 275:744-745 [*alias* Zihlman et al. 1978]), we have shown that the Midget Gompanzee is a perfect prototype of the Austriopet, since the outlines match perfectly. As can be seen, the differences are very minor, especially if unnecessary detail is omitted. However, the clockwise mode of evolution results in a slight difference in the visual aspect. To avoid confusion, it is recommended that the page is tilted approximately 13° to the right when viewing the Mighty Gompanzee, and the same amount to the left when viewing the Austriopet. The clockwise manner of evolution makes it abundantly clear that the Dizzy Gompanzee is ancestral to the Austriopet, although Latimer et al. would have us believe the opposite. Their objection that the Gompanzee is living at the present day and so cannot be ancestral is absurd. We are all well aware of the notoriously unreliable character of paleontological evidence.

We also give analogous representations of the Great White Chark (*Charkodonta charconodinta charcarodonta*) and the Imperial Ichthyosaur (*Ichthyosaurus guilelmi imperatoris*). The name *Plesiosaurus quadriscissus* is regarded as an abjective synonym, insofar as no scissors have been observed. By omitting incompetent detail, it is evident that the two are prototypic to each other.

It may be noted that the orientations of the Great White Chark and the Imperial Ichthyosaur differ to a greater degree than in the case of the Gumpy Gompanzee and the Austriopet. We are at present unable to account for this, except by postulating a more apomorphic condition, but recommend the reader to avoid confusion

by tilting the paper more steeply than the previous example (~30° or even 45°). This is a preliminary announcement and we hope to return with a fuller discussion in PASTURE, with elimination of remaining incompetent detail. We have already eliminated the traces of knuckle-dusters in the Chark.

References

Latimer, B.M., White, T.D., Kimbel, W.H., Johanson, D.C. & Lovejoy, C.O. 1981. The pygmy chimpanzee is not a living missing link in human evolution. *Journal of Human Evolution* 10:475-488.

Zihlman, A.L., Cronin, J.E., Cramer, D.L. & Sarich, V.M. 1978. Pygmy chimpanzee as a possible prototype for the common ancestor of humans, chimpanzees and gorillas. *Nature* 275:744-745

Acknowledgements

My gratitude is due to Morris Goodman for reading this paper without falling to sleep, at least not perceptibly.

The centenary planning group is deeply grateful that Mikael Fortelius was able to find this unpublished manuscript to use as part of the celebrations.

Environmental volatility and its impact on faunal communities: Insights from Kvabebi (Republic of Georgia)

Alexander Bakhia^{1*}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: alexander.bakhia@helsinki.fi

The Plio-Pleistocene (5 – 2.5 Myr) was a period of significant climatic and environmental instability in Eurasia, which eventually set the stage for the first hominin dispersals into the continent. While the Cenozoic was a time of continuous faunal exchanges between Africa and Eurasia, climatic instability of the Plio-Pleistocene period reduced the frequency and volume of bidirectional dispersals. Without a substantial influx of African species into Eurasia, faunal composition in Eurasia become more complex, yet unique, favouring Eurasian endemism (Frantz *et al.* 2018).

South Caucasus served as an important paleobiogeographic link between Eurasia and Africa. Its complex topography, ideal location and ecosystem diversity offered refuge for diversified mammal communities, of both African and Eurasian origin. Despite its potential as an environmental refugium, the South Caucasus region was also affected by the climatic fluctuations, over time leading to a marked drop in African-related taxa and heightened endemism in the region (Bukhsianidze & Koiava 2018). However, the rate at which this change in the community structure happened in the region remains unclear. Communities that capture this change in the region are either rare, or badly preserved to infer the habitat, behavior and the overall structure of faunal communities during a time of significant change in Eurasia.

The fossil site of Kvabebi (2.8 Myr)(Lazarev *et al.* 2021), located in the Kakheti region, Republic of Georgia, is a prime example of a fossil community shaped by both intercontinental faunal exchanges, and local speciation (Agustí *et al.* 2009) Here, I analyse the diet and body mass of the faunal community to examine diet, niche partitioning and community behaviour at the time of habitat volatility. The results provide valuable insights into the adaptive strategies of faunal communities during periods of climatic instability and emphasize the South Caucasus as a key region for understanding Plio-Pleistocene biogeographic patterns.

Keywords

Plio-Pleistocene, Kvabebi, endemism, Georgia, mesowear, body mass

References

Agustí, J., Vekua, A., Oms, O., Lordkipanidze, D., Bukhsianidze, M., Kiladze, G. & Rook, L. 2009. The Pliocene-Pleistocene succession of Kvabebi (Georgia) and the background to the early human occupation of Southern Caucasus. --- *Quaternary Science Reviews* 28: 3275--3280.

Bukhsianidze, M. & Koiava, K. 2018. Synopsis of the terrestrial vertebrate faunas from the Middle Kura Basin (Eastern Georgia and Western Azerbaijan, South Caucasus). --- *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 63: 441--461.

Frantz, L. A. F., Madsen, O., Megens, H., Groenen, M. A. M. & Lohse, K. 2014. Testing models of speciation from genome sequences: divergence and asymmetric admixture in Island South-East Asian Sus species during the Plio-Pleistocene climatic fluctuations. --- *Molecular Ecology* 23: 5566--5574.

Lazarev, S., Kuiper, K. F., Oms, O., Bukhsianidze, M., Vasilyan, D., Jorissen, E. L., Bouwmeester, M. J., Aghayeva, V., Van Amerongen, A. J., Agustí, J., Lordkipanidze, D. & Krijgsman, W. 2021. Five-fold expansion of the Caspian Sea in the late Pliocene: New and revised magnetostratigraphic and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age constraints on the Akchagylian Stage. --- *Global and Planetary Change* 206: 103624.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2021.103624>

Determining dietary variation and its palaeoecological implications of *Mammuthus primigenius* using mesowear angle analysis

Regan Douglas^{1*}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: regan.douglas@helsinki.fi

Mesowear, a method that scores the wear of teeth to determine the amount of abrasive material in the diet, has long been used to understand palaeoecology through the diet of herbivores. Until recently, proboscidean teeth could not be used for these studies. The method of mesowear angle analysis introduced by Saarinen *et al.* in 2015 has made this possible by measuring the relative angle between the enamel ridges and dentine valleys of the lophs of proboscidean teeth to account for wear. This study compares the average mesowear angles of 428 specimens of Pleistocene *Mammuthus* to determine geospatial variation across the genus, as well as within the species *M. primigenius*. These results are then corroborated with previous studies of other palaeoecological proxies to ensure they truly reflect a means to determine palaeoecology through proboscidean mesowear. Overall, this study finds that significant geospatial variation and little interspecific variation of *Mammuthus* proves that mammoths were highly adaptable herbivores capable of surviving in a wide array of the harshest habitats and browsing or grazing habits were not determined by species morphologies, but by the environments they inhabited.

Keywords

Pleistocene, Proboscidea, Mammoth, Mesowear, Palaeoecology

References

Saarinen, J., Karne, A., Cerling, T., Uno, K., Säilä, L., Kasiki, S., Ngene, S., Obari, T., Mbua, E., Manthi, F.K. & Fortelius, M. 2015. A New Tooth Wear–Based Dietary Analysis Method for Proboscidea (Mammalia). --- *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 35: e918546
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2014.918546>

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Juha Saarinen, as well as Janne Granroth, Björn Kröger, Sami Viljainen, Karin Truuver, George Corner, and Tiffany Adrain for access to specimens and making this study possible.

Anthropocentrism as a source of sampling bias in the fossil record.

T.I.F. Foister^{1*} & O.E. Wilson¹

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: tegan.foister@helsinki.fi

The fossil record is the defining tool of palaeosciences as the only direct evidence of the geographic and temporal distribution of traits, species and lineages. The fossil record preserves a very small percentage of all organisms which have lived on Earth, and the chances of any particular organism being preserved are determined by multiple factors. One such factor is sampling biases, which relate to how likely a fossil is to be collected and recorded in the fossil record. We have examined how focusing on a single taxonomic group (in this case hominins) can be considered as an example of sampling bias on a global Cenozoic scale.

We have investigated the extent to which anthropocentric data collection has contributed to sampling bias in the assembly of the mammalian fossil record (represented by the NOW database). We have found that the current fossil record is anthropocentrically biased both temporally and spatially. Locality density is higher in time slices where hominins are found, and in known hominin bearing countries, such as Spain and Kenya. Our study demonstrates the need to stop essentializing the narrative of human evolution to reduce bias in sampling of fossil localities.

Whilst the fossil record can be applied to many open questions in palaeontology, inescapably, one of the critical questions facing all scientific disciplines today is the current biodiversity crisis. It has been argued that the most valuable data palaeosciences can contribute towards resolving questions of this biodiversity crisis is by providing a baseline of undisturbed communities and ecosystems. The sampling bias towards hominin-bearing sites is a serious limiting factor on our ability to provide data to contribute towards this goal and we suggest this should be used to influence future sampling effort.

Keywords

Fossil prospecting, collection bias, humans, anthropocentrism, spatiotemporal variation

Unraveling the complexity of cave bear molars: the influence of enamel distribution and enamel dentine junction shape

Mebin George Varghese^{1*}, Otto Stenberg¹, Susanna Sova^{1,2}, Jukka Jernvall^{1,2}

1. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: mebin.georgevarghese@helsinki.fi

The cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*), an iconic extinct species from Europe and Western Asia, evolved specialized dentition characterized by large molars with broad chewing surfaces and numerous low, rounded cusps (Kurtén 1995). Since tooth shape is closely linked to feeding behavior, the increasing complexity of cave bear molars suggests a strong reliance on tough plant material. Given that enamel distribution across the chewing surface is rarely uniform, the question arises: how much of the molar complexity in cave bears is due to enamel distribution, and how much is influenced by the shape of the underlying enamel-dentine junction (EDJ)? Additionally, how do these features compare to those of living bear species?

To address this, we used 3D X-ray microtomography (μ CT) to scan the second upper molars of different bear species, reconstructing both enamel and EDJ shapes. We analyzed these features using Orientation Patch Count (OPC) (Evans *et al.* 2007), and enamel thickness measurements. Nutrient-limited model of enamel matrix secretion (Häkkinen *et al.* 2019) and geometric extrapolation of the enamel surface were used to examine variations in enamel distribution. Our findings indicate that the complexity of cave bear molars is not simply a geometric projection of the EDJ; instead, subtle EDJ features are amplified on the enamel surface. This suggests that much of the high molar complexity in cave bears is shaped during the enamel matrix secretion phase. Additionally, cave bears exhibit thicker and more variable enamel compared to their extant relatives.

Keywords

Cave bears, dental morphology, tooth complexity, μ CT, enamel thickness

References

Evans, A. R., Wilson, G. P., Fortelius, M., & Jernvall, J. 2007. High-level similarity of dentitions in carnivorans and rodents. --- *Nature* 445: 78--81.

Kurtén, B. 1995. *The cave bear story: life and death of a vanished animal*. Columbia University Press, New York.

Häkkinen, T. J., Sova, S. S., Corfe, I. J., Tjäderhane, L., Hannukainen, A., & Jernvall, J. 2019. Modeling enamel matrix secretion in mammalian teeth. --- *PLoS Computational Biology* 15: e1007058.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007058>

Macroevolution of functional traits in mammal communities in the Pliocene to modern Omo-Turkana Basin

Jeremias Glögger^{1,2*}, Rebecca M. Muriuki^{1,2,3}, Abigail K. Parker², Daniel Burgas Riera⁴, Juha Saarinen¹, Mar Cabeza Jaimejuan^{5,6}, Rahab N. Kinyanjui^{3,7,8}, Indrė Žliobaitė^{1,2,9}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
2. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, P.O. box 68, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
3. Department of Earth Sciences, National Museums of Kenya, Museum Hill, P.O. BOX 40658-00100, Nairobi, Kenya
4. Department of Biological and Environmental Science, University of Jyväskylä, P.O. Box 35, Ylistönrinne, Surfontie 9 C, FI-40014 Jyväskylä, Finland
5. Organismal and Evolutionary Biology Research Program, Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Helsinki, PO Box 65, Viikinkaari 1, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
6. Helsinki Institute of Sustainability Science (HELSUS), University of Helsinki, Yliopistonkatu 3, FI-00014 Helsinki, Finland
7. Department of Archaeology, Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology, Kahlaische Strasse 10 07745, Jena, Germany
8. Human Origins Program, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, National Mall 10th St. & Constitution Ave. NW, 20560, Washington D.C., USA
9. Finnish Museum of Natural History LUOMUS, P.O. Box 68, FI-00014 University of Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: jeremias.glogger@helsinki.fi

Animals are closely connected to their host ecosystem through functional traits that reflect adaptations to climatic conditions and vegetation cover. By applying uniformitarian principles in ecometric models, we can infer characteristics of past and future ecosystems from present associations between traits distribution across mammal communities and their environments. Our study investigates these functional relationships and their potential change over time. The Omo-Turkana Basin in East Africa is an exceedingly well-studied region that has undergone considerable environmental changes in the course of its geological history. Major changes in community composition through speciation and migration have been attributed to the continuous reconfiguration of the environment. Despite immense interest in the region and decades of research, the wealth of available data has not been reported in a synthesized form thus far. We present a revision and compilation of localities, stratigraphic sections, species occurrences, and morphological traits of the mammal record of the Plio-Pleistocene Omo-Turkana Basin. This dataset is based on the NOW Database, literature reviews and detailed records of seminal work by leading researchers. We use these data for ecometric analyses of dental traits and body mass in large herbivorous mammals at high spatial and temporal resolution. The resultant estimates of paleoenvironmental conditions allow for detection of potential changes in associations between mammal communities and their surroundings over time. We investigate whether modern ecosystems, greatly impacted by human activities and impoverished in biodiversity, are functionally disconnected from the dynamics of past ecosystems and thus inadequate for uniformitarian ecological inferences. The compiled data add new localities, species, and dental traits, enabling broader synthesis and higher resolution faunal studies than have been previously possible in the Omo-Turkana mammalian record.

Keywords

Mammal, Macroevolution, Paleoecology, Functional traits, Omo-Turkana Basin, NOW Database

Acknowledgements

Funding for this work was received from the Research Council of Finland, project no. 354228 to IŽ

Comparison of carpal and tarsal bone anatomy of cave bears and modern ursids

Ronja Hirvonen^{1*}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: ronja.hirvonen@helsinki.fi

Cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*) is an extinct species of bears that lived in Eurasia during the Pleistocene and went extinct around 24,000 years ago. Even though it is one of the most abundant species in the fossil record of its time, the cave bear's environment and adaptations and behaviour in that environment are still largely unknown. This thesis aims to answer the question about the cave bear's environment and adaptations through looking at the carpal and tarsal bones and comparing them to its closest living relatives, the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) and the polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*). The morphology of tarsal and carpal bones can tell us a lot about the behaviour of an animal. The methods utilized in this study are linear measuring and 3D modelling using Polycam, a 3D modelling application. The resulting data will be evaluated and visualized using principal component analysis. Our hypothesis is that the cave bears' tarsals and carpals will resemble those of the brown bear more than those of the polar bear, resulting from their similar living environments. Secondly, we hypothesize that the cave bear tarsals will nonetheless differ notably from those of the brown bear, giving us an insight into the bear's unique adaptations and perhaps aiding our understanding on why the cave bear went extinct while the brown bear and the polar bear managed to survive.

Keywords

Cave bear, Pleistocene, *Ursus spelaeus*, ursids, morphology, 3D modelling

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor Suvi Viranta, senior university lecturer at the department of Anatomy and docent at the Department of Geosciences and Geography at University of Helsinki for guidance. Secondly, I thank Associate Professor Daniela Kalthoff and Associate Professor Thomas Mörs from the Swedish Museum of Natural History and the head Engineer and collection manager Lars Erik Johannessen from the Natural History Museum of Oslo, all for helping me gather comparative material. Lastly, I would like to thank the board of the Master's thesis grant for granting me funding for sample collecting in Stockholm and in Oslo.

Using a Single Gene to Gradually Increase Tooth Complexity

Aida Kaffash Hoshjar^{1*}, Otto Stenberg¹, Outi Hallikas¹, Jukka Jernvall^{1,2}

1. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: aida.kaffashhoshjar@helsinki.fi

The mammalian molar tooth is a notable example of evolving novel morphologies through increased morphological complexity. Several genes crucial for normal patterning of tooth are known to affect molar complexity when mutated. In contrast to the evolutionary trends, the predominant effect of gene mutations is a decrease in dental complexity. A marked exception is *Sostdc1*, a WNT and BMP inhibitor, where loss of function increases dental complexity. The null mutation in mice results in altered cusp patterns and extra teeth, with changes exceeding the evolutionary diversity of rodent molars. Since *Sostdc1*^{+/-} mice appear normal, we explored the link between *Sostdc1* expression and molar complexity by generating *Sostdc1* hypomorphs using CRISPR-Cas9. First, we created *Sostdc1* knockout mice and mice lacking an enhancer region. By crossing these lines with wild-type mice and with each other, we produced five lines with varying reductions in *Sostdc1* expression compared to wild-type. To quantify molar complexity, we used a method of dental topographic analysis, orientation patch count (OPC) from micro-CT reconstructions molars. RT-qPCR contrasted signalling with complexity. Results show gradual changes in morphology with reduced *Sostdc1* expression, and a jump in complexity after a threshold.

Keywords

Molar complexity, gene expression threshold, *Sostdc1*, OPC

Fine-tuned optical character recognition for dental fossil markings

Riikka Korolainen^{1*}

1. Faculty of Science, University of Helsinki, P. O. Box 68, Pietari Kalmin katu 5, FI-00014 University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: riika.korolainen@outlook.com

Digitising and uniformising the structure of handwritten fossil catalogues exhibits a great potential for increasing the accuracy of palaeontological data analysis by increasing sample sizes. Approximately 90, 000 of such samples reside in the archives of the National Museum of Kenya, and an ongoing effort is to store this data in a digital format for better accessibility. A previous project utilized a commercial optical character recognition service for automated reading of these catalogues. This generalist handwriting detection model lacked the ability to detect special characters used to denote tooth samples and could not utilize prior knowledge of the vocabulary that is more likely to be present in the data, leading to loss of information and detection mistakes.

This thesis aims to build a specialist character recognition model to increase the accuracy of the bone or tooth type specifying column of the digitized data by fine-tuning a state-of-the-art optical character recognition model with few-shot transfer learning. This is performed by first finding most accurate recognition models, variants of convolutional neural networks or vision transformers, and most successful transfer learning methods for adapting a model to a new character set. Then, the character recognition accuracy of combinations of these methods are benchmarked using hand-labelled image segments from the fossil catalogues. The final aim of this work is to use the best- performing model to obtain an accurate reading of the catalogues of the National Museum of Kenya, and publish the final model to be used by the paleontological community for further digitization efforts.

Keywords

Optical character recognition, few-shot transfer learning, vision transformers, convolutional neural networks, palaeontological databases

The shape of speed: using 3D humerus shape to track the evolution of cursoriality in fossil canids

Sierra Lopezalles^{1,2*}

1. Department of Biology, Indiana University, 1001 E. 10th Street, Bloomington, IN 47401, USA
2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: slopezal@iu.edu

Estimates of running speed are useful for many kinds of paleontological reconstructions, including the co-evolution of predators and prey and inferring the hunting strategies of extinct species, however previous studies have failed to find a significant relationship between skeletal morphology and speed. This study capitalizes on the high degree of variation in morphology and functional ability across domestic dog breeds to investigate whether shape data can be used for estimating running speed effectively. Here I utilize three-dimensional landmark-based geometric morphometrics and the exceptional historical records from competitive dog races to assess the relationship between humerus shape and relative maximum running speed across dog breeds. Selective breeding of dogs has pushed the morphological variation in dog breeds to the extremes, creating breeds with a variety of humeral shapes and a wide range of maximum running speeds from the Basset Hound at 34 km/h to the Grey Hound at 65 km/h. For each breed, maximum running speed was determined using records from the American Kennel Club's Fast Coursing Agility Test, which is a timed 100-yard sprint. Speeds were normalized by calculating their Froude number and then regressed onto shoulder height in order to obtain an accurate metric of breeds that are fast for their size. Results indicate that there is a strong and significant relationship between the maximum relative speed of the breed and shape of the humerus driven by a combination of the shape of the distal articulation and bone robustness ($R^2 = .47$, $p < .001$). Tests of this dog-based predictive equation on wild canids have low error rates (%SEE = 12.9%, PPE = 12.4%) and support the use of these methods to estimate locomotor performance in fossil canids. Additionally, this method is applied to estimate maximum running speed in a selection of fossil canids, including the dire wolf.

Keywords

Functional morphology, mammals, maximum running speed, geometric morphometrics, post-crania

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank David Polly for his advice and assistance in preparing this paper. Also thanks to Rachel Baumgardner, Jimmy Lattimer, and the University of Missouri at Columbia Veterinary Health Center for allowing me access to their database of dog CT scans, to Adam Ferguson and Bill Simpson at the Field Museum, and to Darrin Lunde, John Ososky, and Teresa Hsu at the National Museum of Natural History for their aid in accessing their respective collections.

Proboscidean post-cranial morphometrics and ecomorphology and their utility in reconstructing past environments

Pauline Mbethe Mbatha^{1*}, Juha Saarinen¹, Jukka Jernvall^{1,2}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
2. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: pauline.mbatha@helsinki.fi

I explore key postcranial features that can be used to differentiate and identify new bones, podials, and metapodials of proboscideans, in particular true elephants of genera *Elephas*, *Loxodonta*, *Mammuthus*, and *Palaeoloxodon*. Understanding of the post-cranial differences in morphology and morphometrics between recent and fossil proboscidean taxa is currently lacking. Therefore, expansion of ecometric analyses of limb bones for proboscideans will be very important. This process will involve establishing morphometric criteria from extant and skeletal fossils collections in Africa and Europe for the postcranial differences of these genera, which could be applied to identifying partial skeletons and isolated post-cranial bone specimens. Ultimately, understanding the post-cranial differences between proboscidean taxa serves as an important starting point for understanding how such postcranial traits in proboscideans can be used in palaeo-environmental reconstruction and how such traits serve as adaptations to move in different environments (e.g. forest elephants moving in closed environments vs “savannah” elephants moving in open environments). This project will also involve description of a very important complete skeleton of cf. *Elephas recki* from Koobi Fora area 123, stored at Turkana Basin Institute facilities, in a comparative framework with other elephant fossils from Koobi Fora, Ileret, West Turkana, and Omo (Ethiopia). This study will be highly valuable because it will lay out a foundation for future work on potential ecometric value of proboscidean post-cranial bones. Additionally, this project could also inform us about habitat needs of extant elephants for conservation efforts.

Plant functional traits as a proxy to reconstruct climate and mammal interactions: links in modern to Miocene ecosystems in Eastern Africa.

Rebecca M. Muriuki^{1,2,3*}, Jeremias Glöggler^{1,2}, Rahab N. Kinyanjui^{3,4,5}, Indrė Žliobaitė^{1,2,6}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, P.O. box 68, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

3. Department of Earth Sciences, National Museums of Kenya, Museum Hill, P.O. BOX 40658-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

4. Department of Archaeology, Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology, Kahlaische Strasse 10 07745, Jena, Germany

5. Human Origins Program, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, National Mall 10th St. & Constitution Ave. NW, 20560, Washington D.C., USA

6. Finnish Museum of Natural History LUOMUS, P.O. Box 68, FI-00014 University of Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: rebecca.muriuki@helsinki.fi

The synthesis of terrestrial plant communities and fossilized botanical remains is challenging—the further we go to the past, the less overlap between taxonomic communities is expected. Comparing the traits of modern plants with those preserved in fossil record can help to overcome this challenge. Plant functional traits are the primary attributes related to plant growth, adaptability and post-mortem taphonomic processes. Various studies have examined how plants respond to climate change across environmental gradients. However, it remains unclear whether these functional traits can be effectively used to trace plant evolution through time.

This study aims to quantify and analyse the functional traits of contemporary plants as analogues, ranging from the present day and back to the Miocene period in the Eastern Africa region. We present data obtained during our field expedition as well as data sourced from published literature. We have compiled plant data from 14 national parks in the region and categorized their functional traits by family and species. Inspection of specimens was done on collections at the University of Helsinki herbarium and East African herbarium, National Museums of Kenya. Traits coding followed the standards of the TRY Database and CLAMP, whereas climate data (elevation, temperature and precipitation) was obtained from WorldClim.

For our preliminary analysis, we are examining 7 plant functional traits in relation to climate variables. We aim to understand, which plant communities and their functional traits can better predict climate, and thus can be used to trace back plant evolution and their interactions with mammals. Data analysis will be conducted using statistical predictive modelling approaches and visualizations, to identify which plant traits are strong indicators of climate across all the parks. We will develop models by creating models to analyse plant associations and herbivores communities in relation to climate.

Keywords

Functional traits, botanical, Eastern Africa, CLAMP, WorldClim, NOW database

Acknowledgements

Funding for this work was received from the Research Council of Finland, project no. 354228 (to IŽ).

What did *Ursus spelaeus* hear? Auditory abilities of the cave bear

Sirpa Nummela^{1*}, Suvi Viranta²

1. Department of Biosciences, Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Helsinki, PO Box 65 Viikinkaari 1, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland.

2. Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Helsinki, PO Box 63, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: sirpa.nummela@helsinki.fi

The European Pleistocene cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*) is an extinct species with larger body size than the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*). According to numerous earlier studies on craniodental aspects, the cave bears are thought to be omnivorous. The graviportal postcranial anatomy suggests adaptation for mountainous habitat and slow, but powerful gait. Here, we widen the study of the cave bear into the field of sensory biology, by focusing on the ear and hearing. We studied the skulls and skull fragments, mainly temporal bones, from Odesa, Ukraine, belonging to the Alexander von Nordmann collection at the Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki. We measured a few middle ear parameters: the tympanic membrane area, malleus mass and length, and stapes mass and footplate area. These data, together with the extrapolations based on them, suggest that the cave bear heard ultrasonic frequencies well, with a high-frequency hearing limit close to 30 kHz. Earlier studies have shown that both the brown bear and the polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*) are more sensitive than mammals in general in their olfaction, but less sensitive in their vision and hearing. The cave bear middle ear parameters place it among these other bear species. With these data, we extend our auditory analysis to comparing bears to other carnivores, focusing especially on the differences between Ursidae and Canidae.

Keywords

Sensory biology, Middle ear, Skull, Pleistocene, Ursidae, Canidae

Acknowledgements

We thank Björn Kröger at the Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki for providing access to collections under his care. Financial support was provided by Svenska Kulturfonden to SN.

Assessment of bias in Pleistocene mammal assemblages and application of recommender systems to improve fossil community sampling

Abigail K. Parker^{1*}, Liping Liu^{2,3,4}, Diana Pushkina², and Indrė Žliobaitė^{1,2,5}

1. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, P.O. box 68, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
3. The Swedish Museum of Natural History, P.O. Box 50007, Frescativägen 40, SE-11418 Stockholm, Sweden
4. Bolin Center for Climate Research, Stockholm University, P. O. Box 50741, Svante Arrheniusväg 8, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden
5. Finnish Museum of Natural History LUOMUS, P.O. Box 68, FI-00014 University of Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: abigail.parker@helsinki.fi

Palaeontological and ecometric studies seeking to understand how animal communities and their environments changed over time face persistent challenges due to the incompleteness of the fossil record. Biases in taphonomy and collection efforts mean that different fossil sites preserve different partial snapshots of past animal communities. In this work, we quantify biases in body size and diet in the fossil record of Pleistocene mammals of Eurasia (The NOW Community 2024), then apply a novel method based on recommender systems modelling (Žliobaitė 2022) to estimate more complete fossil mammal faunas. First, we discriminate large mammal sites, small mammal sites, and mixed sites based on body mass distributions and compare these three site types against modern Eurasian mammal communities (Faurby *et al.* 2018, Mechenich & Žliobaitė 2023). Both large and small mammal sites have relatively more herbivores than modern communities. Mixed-mass sites fall within the range of modern variation in the proportions of large vs. small mammals and diet types occurring together. However, mixed sites are a minority in this record, so we focus on the large mammal fossil faunas, which comprise more than 60% of databased sites, and particularly on their herbivores. We apply recommender systems modelling to identify patterns of co-occurrences within a site/occurrence matrix summarising the faunas. The output of the recommender systems are estimates of which taxa are missing from each site, based on their observed co-occurrences with other taxa across the entire set of sites. Finally, we use ecometric models based on the dental traits of large herbivores to estimate paleoclimatic conditions at the large mammal sites based on both their observed faunal occurrences and the occurrences estimated by the recommender systems. Because the recommender output communities have more continuous trait distributions, the ecometric estimates from those communities yield lower prediction anomalies relative to other proxies than ecometric model estimates derived from raw fossil occurrences.

Keywords

Bias, body size, recommender systems, ecometrics, predictive modelling

References

The NOW Community. 2024. *New and Old Worlds Database of Fossil Mammals (NOW)*. Licensed under CC BY 4.0. Retrieved from <http://www.helsinki.fi/science/now/>.

Žliobaitė, I. 2022. Recommender systems for fossil community distribution modelling. --- *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 13: 1690--1706. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13916>

Faurby, S., Davis, M., Pedersen, R. Ø., Schowanek, S. D., Antonelli, A. & Svenning, J.-C. 2018. PHYLACINE 1.2: The Phylogenetic Atlas of Mammal Macroecology. --- *Ecology* 99: 2626.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.2443>

Mechenich, M. F., & Žliobaitė, I. 2023. Eco-ISEA3H, a Machine Learning Ready Spatial Database for Ecometric and Species Distribution Modeling. --- *Scientific Data* 10: 77. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-01966-x>.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge funding from the Research Council of Finland project “Environments and energy use of early humans on the edge” (no. 341623 to IŽ). Thanks to Kari Lintulaakso and an anonymous reviewer for their feedback on our article in the Björn Kurtén centenary volume, which improved this work. Further thanks to the members of the Björn Kurtén Club for many productive discussions of palaeontology and for their efforts organising this symposium.

The ecology of extinct birds during the Late Pleistocene and its implications to the Late Quaternary extinction event

Ilari Pätälä^{1*}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: ilari.patila@helsinki.fi

The Late Pleistocene saw the extinctions of dozens of species of large mammals across all continents except for Antarctica (Galetti *et al.* 2018). Colloquially known as megafauna, these large herbivores and carnivores have sparked the imagination of the general public and scientists alike, and dozens of papers have been written on these remarkable animals, examining multiple aspects including their ecology, diet, life appearance, and ancient DNA. However, many other species also disappeared during this time, including small mammals, reptiles, and crucially for this study, birds. Over 150 bird species across multiple families went extinct during the Pleistocene, and the overall trends of these extinctions remain largely a mystery (Tyrberg 2008). Recent research has implied that most species of extinct Pleistocene megafauna would have been keystone species, which would have had a huge impact to multiple species sharing their environment (Galetti *et al.* 2018). With this aspect in mind, this study attempts to gather whether most of the bird species that went extinct on continents during the Late Pleistocene would have had an ecological benefit from mammalian megafauna. These include species that interacted with megafauna directly, like scavengers and symbiotic species, or indirectly via habitat maintenance and clearing by megafauna. Using a dataset of extinct bird species with different aspects of their ecology reconstructed by inferring said datapoints from their closest living relatives, this seems to have been the case. A large number of the bird species in the dataset lived in wetlands and open habitats, and these benefited from the habitat maintenance of megafauna (Pearce *et al.* 2023). A large number of carrion feeding birds also became extinct. However, a number of forest species also became extinct, as did many carnivorous and herbivorous birds. These species likely did not interact with megafauna directly, but still may have been impacted by habitat clearing and maintenance by large mammalian herbivores (Pearce *et al.* 2023).

Keywords

Quaternary, Pleistocene, megafauna, palaeoecology, palaeornithology

References

Galetti, M., Moleón, M., Jordano, P., Pires, M. M., Guimarães, P. R., Pape, T., Nichols, E., Hansen, D., Olesen, J. M., Munk, M., de Mattos, J. S., Schweiger, A. H., Owen-Smith, N., Johnson, C. N., Marquis, R. J., Svenning, J.-C. 2018 Ecological and evolutionary legacy of megafauna extinctions. --- *Biological Reviews* 93: 845--862.

Tyrberg, T. 2008. The Late Pleistocene Continental Avian extinction – an evaluation of the fossil evidence. -- *ORYCTOS* 7: 249--269.

Pearce, E. A., Mazier, F., Normand, S., Fyfe, R., Andrieu, V., Bakels, C., Balwierz, Z., Bińka, K., Boreham, S., Borisova, O. K., Brostrom, A., de Beaulieu, J.-L., Gao, C., González-Sampériz, P., Granoszewski, W., Hrynowiecka, A., Kołaczek, P., Kuneš, P., Magri, D., Malkiewicz, M., Mighall, T., Milner, A. M., Möller, P., Nita, M., Noryskiewicz, B., Agnieszka Pidek, I., Reille, M., Robertsson, A.-M., Sakari Salonen, J., Schläfli, P., Schokker, J., Scussolini, P., Šeirienė, V., Strahl, J., Urban, B., Winter, H. & Svenning, J.-C. 2023. Substantial light woodland and open vegetation characterized the temperate forest biome before *Homo sapiens* --- *Science Advances* 9: eadi9135. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adi913>

Pleistocene paleoecology and body mass of horses in northern Eurasia.

Diana Pushkina^{1,2*}

1. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, P.O. box 68, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland
2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: diana.pushkina@gmail.com

The “grazing horses” (Equinae) were successful large herbivores that arrived from North America to Eurasia at the Plio-Pleistocene boundary. The adaptiveness of high-crowned (hypsodont) *Equus spp.* allowed them to conquer environments from open to forested, resulting in different body sizes. Despite controversial systematics of Equidae, their ecomorphological features are quantifiable. The Pleistocene habitat and *Equus spp.* body mass changes were studied across Northern Eurasia based on the NOW database (The NOW Community 2024) and literature. Mean non-equid ungulate hypsodonty demonstrated progressive opening of landscapes throughout the Pleistocene, returning towards more humid and closed environments south of 70°N at the very end of the Pleistocene and during the Holocene, corresponding to the modern boreal forest (taiga) zonation. Landscape heterogeneity across Northern Eurasia indicated different zoogeographic provinces. The body mass of horses varied temporally and geographically, and decreased from the Pleistocene to the Holocene. A noticeable decrease occurred between the early Middle and late Middle Pleistocene, corresponding to global climatic and environmental changes (Galerian- Aurelian or Tiraspol – Khazar faunal exchange). Although large horses are usually associated with more closed habitats and have more mixed diets, whereas small horses are usually associated with open habitats and are grazers (Saarinen *et al.* 2021), some cases are found with a contrasting pattern across Northern Eurasia. Such cases mostly occur in the highest latitudes, where temperature or cold climate rather than precipitation or aridity could have driven the “harshness” and openness of these environments, but are worth investigating more thoroughly. The Holocene domestication might have prevented small-sized and grazing-adapted horse lineages from extinction when taiga forests spread across Northern Eurasia.

Keywords

Equidae, horses, body mass, hypsodonty, Northern Eurasia, aridity, taiga, Pleistocene, Holocene.

References

The NOW Community. 2024. *New and Old Worlds Database of Fossil Mammals (NOW)*. Licensed under CC BY 4.0. Retrieved from <http://www.helsinki.fi/science/now/>.

Saarinen, J., Cirilli, O., Strani, F., Meshida, K. & Bernor, R. L. 2021. Testing equid body mass estimate equations on modern zebras with implications to understanding the relationship of body size, diet and habitats of *Equus* in the Pleistocene of Europe. --- *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 9: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.622412>

Acknowledgements

I thank the Helsinki palaeontological community and the organizing committee of the Björn Kurtén Centenary for their work in bringing this volume and symposium together, as well as Christine Janis, Omar Cirilli and Juha Saarinen and Krzysztof Raciborski for their valuable feedback on the article in this volume.

Tooth development and diversity in squamate reptiles

Daria Razmadze^{1*}, Julia Eymann¹, Nicolas Di-Poi¹

1. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: daria.razmadze@helsinki.fi

Teeth have played a crucial role in the evolution of jawed vertebrates, impacting feeding, social interactions, and reproduction. While modern insights into tooth development mainly stem from mouse studies, squamate reptiles (lizards and snakes) are ideal model systems for exploring important aspects of vertebrate tooth diversity, especially those unique to non-mammalian species. Due to their remarkable diversity, squamates exhibit a variety of ecologies and dental phenotypes that reflect ecological specialization. Lizards, in particular, display many lesser-studied and ancestral dental traits such as tooth renewal (polyphyodonty), complex tooth structures (multicuspidy), and varied dentitions along the jaw (heterodonty). In this research, we employed a multidisciplinary approach to investigate tooth development in four lizard species with different dentition types. We gathered data on both the overall dentition patterning along the jaw and the development of individual teeth. Our findings reveal that key aspects of reptile dental development vary among lizard species and differ from typical mammalian patterns. Notably, the enamel knot, a well-known signalling centre in mammals, is present in all studied species, indicating its highly conserved role in tooth development among vertebrates. These insights enhance our understanding of the evolution and diversity of vertebrate dentitions.

Keywords

Squamates, dentition, enamel knot, morphogenesis

How do developmental constraints and functional demands affect evolution of the mammalian post-canine dentition?

Kat Sestrick^{1,2*}

1. Department of Biology, Indiana University, 1001 E. 10th Street, Bloomington, IN 47401, USA
2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: ksestric@iu.edu

Kurtén was a pioneer in asking how processes of development affect morphological variation and therefore evolution. I addressed that question by asking how the evolvability of the mammalian postcanine dentition is affected by two factors: the conflict between developmental constraint and functional demand, and the homogenization of the postcanine tooth row. In the mammalian order Carnivora, the upper tooth row is composed of mesial premolars, a specialized “carnassial” last premolar, and molars. Developmentally, the carnassial is linked to premolars, but functionally it can be more like a premolar, more like a molar, or different than both. For a broad range of species that capture all three functional conditions, I measured whether the carnassial covaried more strongly with molars or with the teeth in its functional grouping using both total variation (which is influenced by functional selection) and fluctuating asymmetry (which is influenced by developmental processes). For each, I estimated the relative eigenvalue variation (a tool for estimating the number of independent modules) and two-block partial least squares correlation between the shapes of individual teeth. In the raccoon (*Procyon lotor*), the fourth upper premolar resembles a molar in function and thus presents a conflict between the developmental and functional basis for covariation. Compared to related carnivoran taxa without this conflict, the raccoon displays a stronger grouping of the fourth premolar with the molar, less support for developmentally defined modularity, but no change in overall integration. Patterns of modularity and correlation have been altered in the raccoon without changing overall evolvability. To study how tooth row homogenization affects the system, I compared two primate species: *Eulemur albifrons*, a lemur with a non-homogenous tooth row retaining differentiation between the premolar and molars, and *Papio anubis*, a baboon which has as a homogenous postcanine dentition. Increased homogeneity increases both integration and between-tooth correlation while decreasing developmental modularity. Loss of modularity reflects a decrease in evolvability, making this a state which would be evolutionarily difficult to reverse. The insights gained can help inform the patterns observed in the mammalian fossil record.

Keywords

Developmental constraint, evolvability, mammals, dentition

Acknowledgements

Thank you to Lauren Caspers, Marisa Surovy, and Eleanor Hoeger at the American Museum of Natural History; Ryan Kennedy and Sam Couch with the William R. Adams Zooarchaeology Laboratory; and Teresa Hsu and Darrin Lunde with the National Museum of Natural History for access to specimens for this project.

Detecting the phenotypic effect of rickets in human molars

Susanna Sova^{1,2*}, Mebin George Varghese¹, Teemu Häkkinen³, Leo Tjäderhane⁴, Jukka Jernvall^{1,2}

1. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

3. School of Dentistry, University of California San Francisco, 513 Parnassus Avenue, HSE, #1509, San Francisco, CA 94143, USA

4. Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Diseases, Helsinki University Hospital, PO Box 41, Haartmaninkatu 1, FI-00014 University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: susanna.sova@helsinki.fi

Correctly formed enamel is crucial for tooth function. Severe deficiency of vitamin D, or rickets, disrupts not only the mineralisation but also secretion of enamel matrix, resulting in malformed enamel with pits and/or grooves that are vulnerable to caries. It remains unknown whether the teeth affected by rickets have unique phenotypes, or whether they can be considered extreme cases of normal variation. Identifying subtle effects of vitamin D deficiency could help in the detection of subclinical variation. A methodological challenge to analyse human molars is their variable morphology, hampering the identification of normal and abnormal variation in enamel distribution. We have developed both computational modelling and topographic analyses methods to quantify and classify differences in enamel distribution. Topographic methods, such as OPC (orientation patch account) allow the quantification of phenotypes without landmarks. With computational modelling, we identified topographic features linked to rickets. Topographic analyses of both the enamel surface and underlying enamel-dentin junction show rachitic molars to have similar but more extreme enamel features to our control sample. Some aspects of rachitic molars, however, show similarities to orangutan molars, suggesting distinct effects of the lack of vitamin D. Topographic methods show promise in the analysis of complex phenotypes.

Bretskyan hierarchy, geobiomes and the epoch-scale Miocene contiguous USA mammalian paleobiogeography – the HespDiv approach

Andrej Spiridonov^{1*}, Liudas Daumantas¹, Niles Eldredge²

1. Department of Geology and Mineralogy, Vilnius University, M. K. Čiurlionio 21/27, LT-03103, Vilnius, Lithuania

2. Division of Paleontology, American Museum of Natural History, 200 Central Park West New York, NY 10024-5102, New York, New York, U.S.A

Presenting author's email: andrej.spiridonov@gf.vu.lt

Biotal evolution proceeds in time and space. Space, once a neglected theme, is currently on the pinnacle of theory and the practice of evolutionary paleontological research. It was recently recognized that the structure and dynamic of the planet plays the key role in defining spatio-temporal individuality of ecosystems at all space and time scales, thus 'gluing together' community assemblages and forcing them to coevolve for significant stretches of time (Spiridonov and Eldredge, 2024). The geological and geomorphic structures are scaling in their amplitudes and durations, therefore implying continuous hierarchy of increasingly formidable (with measurement scale) barriers, which implies that the process of allopatry works at multiple scales with increasing significance of barriers at larger scale. The portions of biota which are forcefully individualized by the external factors we call 'geobiomes' – units of biota confined and significantly influenced by geological factors. The geobiomes are hierarchically and contiguously organized, following the hierarchy of barriers which individuate them. This property calls for a new numerical solution in determining the hierarchical contiguous structure of biota. A new family of algorithms was recently presented for solving exactly this kind of problem – the so called HespDiv approach, implemented in a newly developed R package 'hespdiv' (Daumantas and Spiridonov, 2024).

Here we present the results of the application of the HespDiv approach to the terrestrial mammalian fossil record of the Miocene contiguous USA. The approach yielded the hierarchy of contiguous clusters (bioprovinces) with boundaries significant at the epoch scale. The most significant boundary appeared between the southeastern USA (Gulf Coast) and the rest of the area. Monte Carlo sensitivity analysis revealed the probabilistic nature and the level of fuzziness of positions of bioprovince boundaries in relation to the spatial sampling unevenness.

References

Daumantas, L. & Spiridonov, A., 2024. hespdiv: an R package for spatially constrained, hierarchical and contiguous regionalization in palaeobiogeography. --- *Palaeontology* 67: e12702.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/pala.12702>

Spiridonov, A. & Eldredge, N. 2024. The Bretskyan hierarchy, multiscale allopatry, and geobiomes—on the nature of evolutionary things. --- *Paleobiology* 50: 194--213

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the Lithuanian Science Foundation Grant S-MIP-24-62 "Competition and escalation in time and space — Bretskyan hierarchy and the generalized causal theory of evolution and innovations"

Shearing a developmental rule

Otto Stenberg^{1*}, Suvi Viranta², Jukka Jernvall^{1,3}

1. Institute of Biotechnology, P.O. Box 56, FI-00014, University of Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Helsinki, PO Box 63, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

3. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: otto.stenberg@helsinki.fi

Since Kurtén's day, our understanding of the interplay of evolutionary and developmental processes has increased vastly. The question of how developmental realities channel the flow of evolution remains complex beyond doubt, yet some underpinnings of this integration can be indicated clearly enough to be called developmental rules. One such is outlined by the Inhibitory Cascade (IC) model (Kavanagh *et al.* 2007) which explains shared size patterns in mammal molars as a consequence of sequential tooth development. The IC model states that first-developing anterior molars inhibit the growth of the later-developing molars behind them, which leads to a trend of linear tooth size change along the molar row. Molar dentitions with proportions adhering to the expectations of the IC model have been observed in a broad range of mammalian taxa (Kavanagh *et al.* 2007, Halliday & Goswami 2013) — with some exceptions, the most interesting of which may be the family Canidae. Molar size proportions in canid dentitions follow a pattern similar to, yet clearly distinct from that of the general IC model (Asahara 2013).

Here we build upon previous work on IC exceptions (Stenberg *et al.* in press) to seek the proximate cause of this canid dental divergence from what could be considered an overall trend for mammals. We sampled lower molar size proportions in a range of canid taxa, additionally also considering the proportions of trigonid and talonid area in the first molar, the lower carnassial. This follows the line of inquiry by Asahara (2013), who considered the large carnassial the potential cause for the atypical molar proportions in canids.

Keywords

Canids, inhibitory cascade, molar size, carnassial complex

References

Kavanagh, K. D., Evans, A. R. & Jernvall, J. 2007. Predicting evolutionary patterns of mammalian teeth from development. --- *Nature* 449: 427--432.

Halliday, T. J. & Goswami, A. 2013. Testing the inhibitory cascade model in Mesozoic and Cenozoic mammaliaforms. --- *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 13:79. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-13-79>

Asahara, M. 2013. Unique inhibitory cascade pattern of molars in canids contributing to their potential to evolutionary plasticity of diet. --- *Ecology and Evolution* 3, 278--285.

Stenberg, O. E., Moustakas-Verho, J. E. & Jernvall J. 2024. Rewinding developmental trajectories shows how bears break a developmental rule. --- *Annales Zoologici Fennici* 61 (in press).

Application of mesowear to leontiniid notoungulates: diet in *Taubatherium paulacoutoi*

Oscar E. Wilson^{1*}, Juha Saarinen¹

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

Presenting author's email: oscar.wilson@helsinki.fi

The Late Oligocene (Deseadan SALMA) Taubaté fauna of the Tremembé formation, São Paulo State, Brazil, contains a diverse vertebrate assemblage with at least 11 described mammal species (Carmo *et al.* 2024). Of these, the most abundant is *Taubatherium paulacoutoi*, a large, long-necked leontiniid notoungulate. We here apply mesowear (both by traditional cusp scoring and facet angles) to the specimens of *Taubatherium* within the collections of the Museu de História Natural de Taubaté Doutor Herculano Alvarenga (MHNT), as a case study for the application of these methods to leontiniids and other ectolophodont taxa with no modern representatives. Using the traditional cusp-scoring methodology (Fortelius and Solounias 2000), *Taubatherium* lies outside the range of values recorded in any modern taxa, as a consequence of a high proportion of sharp, low cusps, also observed in other notoungulates (Croft and Weinstein 2008). The mean mesowear angle in *Taubatherium* (measured from the ectoloph wear facet) is 78.6°, which is very sharp and comparable to those of modern browsing rhinos like *Dicerorhinus sumatrensis* (75°) and *Diceros bicornis* (77.3°). The sharp mesowear angles are consistent with sharpening attritional wear produced by consumption of browse, and particularly hard components like branches (Popowics & Fortelius 1997). Such a dietary interpretation is also supported by their long necks and postcranial morphology and also matches our observations in other leontiniids. We propose that *Taubatherium* would have browsed in herds around the edges of the lake preserved in this assemblage, consuming perhaps some aquatic vegetation but also the leaves and branches of tropical vegetation in the surrounding valley. Ectoloph wear facets represent a potentially powerful methodology to investigate diet in taxa like leontiniids, where modern representatives are lacking, and where analogues cannot be identified through cusp relief and shape alone.

Keywords

Leontiniidae, Deseadan, mesowear, attrition, *Taubatherium*, Brazil, Oligocene

References

- Carmo, G. M. do, Lima, S. S., Araújo-Júnior, H. I. de, Pinheiro, R. M, Melo, D. J. de & Couto-Ribeiro, G. 2024. Paleo-faunistic checklist of the Tremembé Formation (Oligocene of the Taubaté Basin, Paraíba Valley, Brazil). --- *Terræ Didactica* 20: e024013. <https://doi.org/10.20396/td.v20i00.8674375>
- Croft, D. A. & Weinstein, D. 2008. The first application of the mesowear method to endemic South American ungulates (Notoungulata). --- *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 269:103--114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2008.08.007>
- Fortelius, M. & Solounias, N. 2000: Functional characterization of ungulate molars using the abrasion-attrition wear gradient: a new method for reconstructing paleodiets. *American Museum Novitates* 3301: 1-35.
- Popowics, T. E. & Fortelius, M. 1997. On the cutting edge: Tooth blade sharpness in herbivorous and faunivorous mammals. --- *Annales Zoologici Fennici* 34:73--88.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful for access to the MHNT collections to Graziella do Couto Ribeiro, Diana da Silva and Frederico Nordskog, for modern rhino specimens to Matthew Lowe and Robert Asher (University Museum

of Zoology Cambridge), Ogeto Mwebi, Titus Imboma and Pauline Mbatha (National Museums of Kenya), Janne Granroth, Risto Väinölä and Veronika Laine (Finnish Museum of Natural History), David Kimutai (Tsavo East) and for assistance with the angle measurement process to Hal Wilson. The work was supported by funding from the Research Council of Finland grant NEPA – Non-Analogue Ecosystems of the Past [340775/346292], and a travel grant from the Nordenskiöld Samfundet.

Dental ecometrics as a tracer of climatic change during Late Neogene in the Siwaliks

Sania Zubaid^{1,2*}, Abigail K. Parker², Juha Saarinen¹, Muhammad Tahir Waseem^{3,4}, Indrė Žliobaitė^{1,2}

1. Department of Geosciences and Geography, University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 64, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

2. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, P.O. box 68, Gustaf Hällströmin katu 2, FI-00014, Helsinki, Finland

3. Pakistan Museum of Natural History, Shakarparian National Park, Garden Avenue, Islamabad, Islamabad Capital Territory 44000, Pakistan

4. Pakistan Science Foundation, 1-Constitution Avenue, G-5/2, Islamabad, Islamabad Capital Territory, Pakistan

Presenting author's email: sania.zubaid@helsinki.fi

Siwaliks of Pakistan has been at the crossroads of multiple faunal interchanges throughout the Cenozoic. It has been explored by many researchers during the last two decades in terms of faunal elements in relation to the taxonomy and paleoclimate during the Miocene (Barry *et al.* 2002, Badgley *et al.* 2008, Flynn *et al.* 2016, Nelson 2005, Nelson 2007, Karp *et al.* 2018). In our current studies, we will provide a new integrative understanding of Siwaliks palaeoecological contexts using dental ecometric and mesowear analysis. Therefore, we are analyzing how ecometric dental traits of large mammalian herbivore communities can be used to reliably reconstruct climate and vegetational shifts in the Siwalik from the Miocene to the Pleistocene. Ecometrics is an analytical methodology that quantitatively links trait variables of faunal communities to their environments (Žliobaitė *et al.* 2016, Vermillion *et al.* 2018, Oksanen *et al.* 2019). Dental ecometrics therefore statistically evaluates and interlinks the relationship between dental trait distribution across organismal communities and local environmental conditions. The resulting statistical models can be used for reconstructing environmental conditions of the past based on the fossil organismal communities.

In our preliminary studies we used different dental ecometrics to reconstruct the Siwaliks paleoenvironment and compared which dental traits would give the best predictions in this temporal and regional context. We used mean values of different dental traits over mammalian communities and plotted them against space and time to analyze trends and potential associations with climate. Our findings after preliminary analysis indicated that during the Miocene climatic conditions were warmer and humid (Barry *et al.* 2002), shifting to cooler and arid climatic conditions during the Pleistocene, which supported the climatic and vegetational turnovers. Next, we will use quantitative modelling to carry out continental-scale reconstructions of the climatic and vegetational shift and their effect on mammalian adaptation and dispersal in Asia and other regions. It will help us to answer questions about macroevolution and the functioning of terrestrial ecosystems.

References

Badgley, C., Barry, J. C., Morgan, M. E., Nelson, S. V., Behrensmeyer, A. K., Cerling, T. E. & Pilbeam, D. 2008. Ecological changes in Miocene mammalian record show impact of prolonged climatic forcing. --- *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 105: 12145--12149.

Barry, J. C., Morgan, M. E., Flynn, L. J., Pilbeam, D., Behrensmeyer, A. K., Mahmood Raza, S., Khan, I. A., Badgley, C., Hicks, J. & Kelley, J. 2002. Faunal and Environmental Change in the Late Miocene Siwaliks of Northern Pakistan. --- *Paleobiology* 28:1--71.

Flynn, L. J., Pilbeam, D., Barry, J. C., Morgan, M. E. & Raza, S. M. 2016. Siwalik synopsis: A long stratigraphic sequence for the later Cenozoic of South Asia. --- *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 15: 877--887.

Karp, A. T., Behrensmeyer, A. K. & Freeman, K. H. 2018. Grassland fire ecology has roots in the late Miocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115: 12130--12135.

Nelson, S. V. 2005. Paleoseasonality inferred from equid teeth and intra-tooth isotopic variability. --- *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 222: 122--144.

Nelson, S. V. 2007. Isotopic reconstructions of habitat change surrounding the extinction of *Sivapithecus*, a Miocene hominoid, in the Siwalik Group of Pakistan. --- *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*. 243: 204--222.

Oksanen, O., Žliobaitė, I., Saarinen, J., Lawing, A. M. & Fortelius, M. A. 2019. Humboldtian approach to life and climate of the geological past: estimating palaeotemperature from dental traits of mammalian communities. --- *Journal of Biogeography* 46:1760--1776.

Vermillion W., Polly, P. D., Head, J., Eronen, J. & Lawing, A. M. 2018. Ecometrics: A trait-based approach to paleoclimate and paleoenvironmental reconstruction. --- In: Croft, D. A., Simpson, S. W. & Su, D. F. (eds). *Methods in Paleocology: Reconstructing Cenozoic Terrestrial Environments and Ecological Communities*: 373--394, Springer Nature, Cham.

Žliobaitė, I., Rinne, J., Tóth, A. B., Mechenich, M., Liu, L., Behrensmeyer, A. K. & Fortelius, M. A. 2016. Herbivore teeth predict climatic limits in Kenyan ecosystems. --- *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113: 12751—12756.

Acknowledgements

We thank the "Siwalik Work Group" with John Barry for the species-localities data and guidance. Funding from EDUFI and the Research Council of Finland (no. 341623 to IŽ) is acknowledged.